

FETCH LIMITED WAVE GROWTH OBSERVED
DURING ARSLOE

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ABSTRACT

Wave data collected during ARSLOE at distances 3, 6, 12 and 34 km offshore are used to examine the growth of wind waves with fetch. Non-dimensional energy, \bar{E} , and peak frequency, \bar{f}_m , are computed and related to nondimensional fetch, \bar{X} , for a variety of windspeed and atmospheric stability cases. Relations for \bar{E} vs \bar{X} , \bar{f}_m vs \bar{X} , and \bar{E} vs \bar{f}_m are compared to those reported in the literature. The JONSWAP equations are found to be appropriate, despite the presence of significant swell.

1. INTRODUCTION

In ARSLOE, several gages were deployed in a line perpendicular to shore in order to measure the change in waves propagating from deep to shallow water. Although the primary purpose was to study waves propagating toward the coast, the array also allowed the study of wave growth with offshore winds. The measurement of fetch-limited wavegrowth is important for development and calibration of numerical wave growth models and simple prediction schemes. Although the growth of waves has been studied extensively since World War II, a wide variety of formulae exist and there remains some controversy concerning the coefficients and exponents (Phillips, 1977, Kahma, 1981). In this paper ARSLOE results are compared to some available growth formulae.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

ARSLOE was a joint experiment, involving several U.S. Government agencies, universities, and foreign countries, coordinated by the Coastal Engineering Research Center (CERC). Most of the data were collected at CERC's Field Research Facility (FRF), near Duck, N.C. (Fig. 1.)

From the variety of meteorological and wave sensors used in ARSLOE, a line of 4 buoys aligned perpendicular to the shoreline, along the axis of the pier at the FRF (Fig.1.) was selected for analysis. The buoys provided one-dimensional wave spectra at stations 3, 6, 12 and 34 kilometers off-shore (Table 1). Wind speed and direction as well as air and sea temperatures were obtained from NOAA's XERB buoy at 34 km. Wind speed and direction and air temperature were measured at 10 meters above sea level. The data were recorded

in 20 minute segments regularly at 6 hour intervals and at 1 hour intervals during storms. The spectral analysis of the wave data from buoys 620, 630, 710 was done at CERC, with 4096 points (1024 seconds at 4 hertz) using the FFT method described by Thompson (1972). The analysis of the XERB (34 km) buoy data was performed by the National Data Buoy Office. Considerable care was taken in calibration of the buoys before and after the experiment.

GAGE	DISTANCE FROM SHORE (km)	WATER DEPTH(m)
620	3.2	17
630	5.9	19
710	12.8	25
XERB	33.6	35

TABLE 1 GAGE DISTANCE AND WATER DEPTH

3. SELECTION OF FETCH LIMITED CASES

The shore normal lies at 70.6° True North (TN), so that winds from 250.6° TN are directly offshore. A wave record is considered fetch-limited if the wind blew from 210-290° TN with maximum hourly differences of 15% at speeds 9 m/s with maximum hourly variations of ± 10% for time t (Resio and Vincent, 1979) where:

$$t = \frac{68.8 X^{.67}}{(U_c g)^{.33}} \quad U_c = .71 U^{1.23} \quad (1)$$

U_c is the 10-meter windspeed corrected to reflect the increase in windstress with increased windspeed based on Garratt (1977), g is the gravitational constant, and X is computed fetch in meters. X is computed by

$$X = X_B / \cos(A_w - A_n) \quad (2)$$

where X_B is the shore-normal fetch to the buoy, A_w is wind direction (°TN), and $A_n = 250.6°$ TN is the direction of the shore normal plus 180°. This expression for X is used because the shoreline is a smooth, nearly straight line.

4. FRICTION VELOCITY FROM 10-METER WINDSPEED

The nondimensional energy \bar{E} , fetch \bar{X} , and peak frequency \bar{f}_m were scaled by the friction velocity of air, U_* :

$$\bar{E} = \frac{g^2 E}{U_*^4} \quad \bar{X} = \frac{g X}{U_*^2} \quad \bar{f}_m = \frac{U_* f_m}{g}$$

where E is the record variance (M^2), X is the computed fetch and f_m is the frequency of maximum energy for the fetch-limited component of the spectrum. Other works (Hasselmann et al., 1973, Kahma, 1981) scaled parameters by the 10-meter windspeed U_{10} . Scaling by windspeed alone does not consider the dependence of windstress upon the stability of the air-sea interface.

Friction velocity was computed using the planetary boundary layer model of Resio et al. (in press), which derives from Cardone (1969). Stability of the air-sea interface was taken into effect via the air-sea temperature difference at the 34 km XERB buoy. Table 2 demonstrates the significant dependence of U_* on the air-sea temperature difference. Because U_* was computed from conditions at 34km, it may be only a fair approximation for U_* at the inner buoy locations. The winds at the inner locations may not be beyond land effects and the model assumes an open ocean situation. Although the 10-meter winds at 34km are only approximations for the other locations, they were considered reasonable approximations.

	$t_{air} - t_{sea}$ ($^{\circ}C$)	U_* (m/s)
unstable	-15	.43
	-10	.41
	-5	.40
neutral	0	.38
stable	5	.33
	10	.28
	15	.23

TABLE 2. DEPENDENCE OF U_* UPON Δt WHEN $U_{10} = 10$ m/s

5. WAVE CONDITIONS

Hasselmann et al. (1973) attribute the shift of peak towards lower frequencies to nonlinear wave-wave interactions. Figure 2 shows one example of this spectral development. Swell has been removed for this illustration. The behavior of the spectra in a fetch-limited situation agree qualitatively with that seen in JONSWAP.

The wavelength L, corresponding to the observed peak frequency, has been computed for each buoy from the fetch-limited data. This wavelength has been compared to the water depth D at the buoy to assure that $D > L/2$ or that the waves are deep water waves.

Significant swell was present in cases studied. Other works (e.g. Hasselmann et al., 1973, and Mitsuyasu, 1979) which examined fetch-limited wave growth were careful to consider cases in which no swell was present. Many of the fetch-limited cases were dominated by swell. In order to analyze the

fetch-limited spectrum, the swell components were eliminated. The directional spectrum was available at XERB, so that for a given frequency band the dominant wave direction can be determined. The limited-fetch spectrum is the high frequency bands beginning with the lowest frequency band dominated by waves in an off-shore direction.

The break between the swell and the fetch-limited components of the spectrum was generally located at the lowest trough between the swell peak and the fetch-limited peak. However, there are cases where this break between components is difficult to define. Some of the data scatter may be explained by this uncertainty in the separation between swell and fetch-limited components of the spectrum.

6. \bar{E} vs \bar{X}

Nondimensional energy \bar{E} is plotted against nondimensional fetch \bar{X} in Figure 3. The JONSWAP regression line (Hasselmann et al., 1973) is drawn as the broken line along with the JONSWAP envelope of data. The solid line is the regression line for the ARSLOE data. With one exception, the data falls within the JONSWAP envelope.

Many equations have been found for \bar{E} vs \bar{X} :

- $\bar{E} = 1.6 \times 10^{-4} \bar{X}$ Phillips (1977) (A)
- $\bar{E} = 1.6 \times 10^{-4} \bar{X}$ Hasselmann (1973, JONSWAP) (B)
- $\bar{E} = 1.72 \times 10^{-4} \bar{X}$ Mitsuyasu (1979) (C)
- $\bar{E} = 3.6 \times 10^{-4} \bar{X}$ Kahma (1981) (D)
- $\bar{E} = 1.78 \times 10^{-4} \bar{X}^{.8}$ best fit ARSLOE (E)
- $\bar{E} = 1.1 \times 10^{-4} \bar{X}$ ARSLOE, assume linear (F)

The equations (B), (C), (D) were originally scaled by U_{10} . They are rescaled using U_* where $U_*^2 = C_D U_{10}^2$ and $C_D = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$. For equation (C) Mitsuyasu's $C_D = 1.6 \times 10^{-3}$ was used. Equation (E) was computed via a least-squares power curve fit to the nondimensional data. The correlation was .87. Since the exponent in (E) differs from all others, a linear relation between \bar{E} and \bar{X} was forced to achieve equation (F) with a correlation of .82. The 95% confidence intervals for the coefficient and power in equation (E) bracket the coefficient and power in equation (F) and the power 1. Therefore, it is not possible to reasonably distinguish between (E) and (F). In either case our dependence of \bar{E} on \bar{X} is less than that observed in other works. This may be due to the different computation of U_* or perhaps the influence of swell on the fetch-limited component of the spectrum. However, examination of Figure 3 suggests that some of the systematic deviation from the JONSWAP line is largely due to some of the XERB data, suggesting that there may have been insufficient time for the conditions to become fetch-limited. If the $\bar{X}^{1.0}$ form is taken, the results are similar to (A), (B), and (C), but the coefficient is only one

third that in (D).

7. \bar{f}_m vs \bar{X}

Figure 4 shows nondimensional peak frequency, \bar{f}_m , plotted against \bar{X} . The JONSWAP regression line and data envelope are drawn as in Figure 3. Again the data resides within the JONSWAP envelope. Equations for \bar{f}_m vs \bar{X} are:

$\bar{f}_m = 1.08 \bar{X}^{-.33}$	Hasselmann et al. (1973, JONSWAP)	(G)
$\bar{f}_m = 1.0 \bar{X}^{-.33}$	Toba (1978)	(H)
$\bar{f}_m = 1.0 \bar{X}^{-1/3}$	Mitsuyasu (1979)	(I)
$\bar{f}_m = 1.01 \bar{X}^{-1/3}$	Kahma (1981)	(J)
$\bar{f}_m = .35 \bar{X}^{-.25}$	Phillips (1977)	(K)
$\bar{f}_m = .398 \bar{X}^{-.254}$	ARSLOE data, best fit	(L)
$\bar{f}_m = 1.09 \bar{X}^{-1/3}$	ARSLOE, assume -1/3 power	(M)

Where necessary these formulae have been re-scaled as previously stated. Equation (L) is a best fit regression line to the nondimensional data. It gives a correlation of 0.92 and is similar to that of Phillips (1977), equation (K). For equation (M), a power of -1/3 was forced, to compare to the other works, and a correlation of 0.915 was obtained. Though equation (L) is the best fit, it is statistically indistinguishable from equation (M). If as speculated, some of the XERB data is not quite fetch-limited, the effect would be to move the regression curve more in parallel with the Mitsuyasu-JONSWAP type of relationship.

8. \bar{E} vs \bar{f}_m

\bar{E} is plotted against \bar{f}_m in figure 5. The broken line is from Mitsuyasu (1979). The solid line comes from the regression line for the ARSLOE data. Relations found for \bar{E} vs \bar{f}_m are:

$\bar{E} = 2.4 \times 10^{-6} \bar{f}_m^{-4}$	Phillips (1977, derived)	(N)
$\bar{E} = 2.1 \times 10^{-4} \bar{f}_m^{-3}$	Toba (1978)	(O)
$\bar{E} = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \bar{f}_m^{-3}$	Hasselmann et al. (1973, derived)	(P)
$\bar{E} = 1.7 \times 10^{-4} \bar{f}_m^{-3}$	Mitsuyasu (1979)	(Q)
$\bar{E} = 1.2 \times 10^{-4} \bar{f}_m^{-3.1}$	ARSLOE	(R)

The equation found for ARSLOE is in close agreement with Mitsuyasu. It is interesting to note that the Mitsuyasu and Hasselmann relationship is expected if the \bar{E} - \bar{X} relationship has the 1.0 exponent and a \bar{f}_m - \bar{X} relationship with exponent of -0.33. The Phillips form is a result of an \bar{E} - \bar{X} exponent of 1.0 and an \bar{f}_m - \bar{X} exponent -0.25. In the ARSLOE

case the \bar{E} - \bar{f}_m has exponent of -3.1 as a result of the \bar{E} - \bar{X} exponent of .8 and \bar{f}_m - \bar{X} exponent of 0.254. Since the \bar{E} - \bar{f}_m relationship appears to hold under duration growth as well (Mitsuyasu, 1979) it may appear to be a more fundamental relationship than \bar{E} - \bar{X} or \bar{f}_m - \bar{X} . At least in ARSLOE, it holds even though the \bar{f}_m - \bar{X} derived as a best fit has exponent of 0.254^m. This may be supportive of some of the XERB data not being fetch-limited.

9. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The relationships derived among \bar{E} , \bar{f}_m and \bar{X} from conditions believed to be fetch-limited in ARSLOE have been examined and shown not to be statistically dissimilar from most of the recent field data sets on fetch-limited wave growth. The \bar{E} - \bar{X} relationship had an exponent of 0.8 which is different from previous studies which suggested a value of 1.0. However, when the data is correlated with an $\bar{X}^{-1/3}$ form, the correlation is nearly as high. The situation is similar for the \bar{f}_m - \bar{X} relationship. The best fit power curve is close to Phillips (1977) but if a $\bar{X}^{-1/3}$ form is presumed, the correlation is almost exactly the same. The measured \bar{E} - \bar{f}_m relationship is close to that of Mitsuyasu-Hasselmann.

One conclusion reached is that although a particular set of equations may be achieved through a least-squares procedure, other apparently different equations may fit the data almost as well, particularly if the number of samples is small. Most field studies conducted within this subject area are based on somewhat small data sets and it may well be that some of the differences are due to sampling.

The problem of relating \bar{E} and \bar{X} and \bar{f}_m and \bar{X} has mainly been addressed through field studies with the relationship established empirically. As discussed here, this results in families of curves most of which may not be accepted as statistically different with a high level of confidence. It would be far more comforting to have a physical basis for the \bar{E} - \bar{X} or \bar{f}_m - \bar{X} equation which then is either confirmed or rejected by field data.

Dr. D. T. Resio (personal communication) suggested the basis for an \bar{E} - \bar{X} relationship by noting that the rate of change in momentum of the wave field with time should be equal to that fraction of the incoming momentum from the atmosphere retained by the wave field. Dobson (1971) and Hasselmann et al. (1973) find this nearly constant (5%) with respect to \bar{X} . Letting $M(f)$ be the momentum at a given frequency, $\frac{d}{dt} M(f) df = \lambda \rho_a U_*^2$ where λ is the part of the momentum retained by the waves. This leads to:

$$\rho_w g \int \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{E(f)}{c(f)} \right) df = \lambda \rho_a U_*^2 \quad \text{or:}$$

$$\rho_w g \frac{d}{dx} \int \frac{c_g}{c} E(f) df = \lambda \rho_a U_*^2 \quad \text{or:}$$

$$\frac{\rho_w g}{2} \frac{d\bar{E}}{dx} = \lambda \rho_a U_*^2$$

This can be integrated over fetch to obtain

$$gE = 2\lambda \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_w} U_*^2 X$$

This can be normalized to

$$g \frac{E}{U_*^4} = 2\lambda \frac{\rho_a g X}{\rho_w U_*^2}$$

or

$$\bar{E} = 2\lambda \frac{\rho_a \bar{X}}{\rho_w}$$

Taking 5% for λ and .00123 for $\frac{\rho_a}{\rho_w}$ gives

$$\bar{E} = 1.2 \times 10^{-4} \bar{X}$$

which is close to all but Kahma's results. Thus the linear relationship so often found has a theoretical basis as long as λ is constant with respect to fetch. If the $\bar{E} - \bar{X}$ relationship found above is accepted as approximately correct and if the $\bar{E} - \bar{f}_m$ relationship is as found in field data, then the $\bar{f}_m - \bar{X}$ relationship should have the exponent $-.33$ and not $-.25$. Since the ARSLOE data fits the $\bar{E} - \bar{f}_m$ relationship, and is nearly as well correlated with the linear $\bar{E} - \bar{X}$ and the $-.33$ exponent $\bar{f}_m - \bar{X}$ relationship as the best fit conditions, we conclude that the data is supportive of the Mitsuyasu and JONSWAP type relationships. It is suspected that some of the XERB data is too low, presumably due to not being fully fetch-limited.

The conditions observed here were all measured in the presence of a swell propagating approximately in an opposite direction to the growing wind sea. The result that the fetch growth relationships derived are not much different from the cases where swell was not present suggests that the interaction of the sea and swell does not dominate or greatly alter the development of the wind sea at the fetches studied. In general, f_m of the sea was at least 2 f_m of the swell.

The data set used was a data set of opportunity and therefore has some drawbacks. Foremost is the absence of a meteorological measuring system at each gage site. Observations of the windspeed during offshore winds indicated some increase in windspeeds in the offshore direction. The development of the marine boundary layer with distance from shore is not well understood. Until U_* or some equivalent parameter is measured in conjunction with the waves along the fetch, it is not clear that any refinement of the basic growth curves is possible.

10. SUMMARY

Fetch-limited wave growth relationships among dimensionless energy, peak frequency and fetch were estimated from ARSLOE data. It was possible to show that the data were consistent with the Mitsuyasu-JONSWAP forms of the relationships, although they were not the best fits in the least squares sense. It was possible to show that the linear $\bar{E} - \bar{X}$ relationship can be obtained on theoretical grounds. This, coupled

with the $\bar{E} - \bar{f}_m$ relationship, implies that the $\bar{f}_m - \bar{X}$ relationship should be based on $\bar{X}^{-.33}$. It is noted that results are obtained in the presence of significant swell.

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Figure 1. Buoy locations

Figure 2. Wave spectra

Figure 3. \bar{E} vs \bar{X}

Figure 4. \bar{f}_m vs \bar{X}

Figure 5. \bar{E} vs \bar{f}_m